

Newsletter I

Private Law and the Energy Commons

Dear reader,

You have been in contact or collaborated with the EU-funded project ‘Private Law and the Energy Commons’. It is with great pleasure that we give you an update on the most important activities and publications of the project.

FINAL CONFERENCE for scientists and practitioners: Turin (Italy), 27-28 March

On 27 and 28 March 2024, the University of Turin will be hosting the final conference of the project, entitled ‘Private Law in the Energy Commons – A Multidisciplinary Challenge’. There will be input from 27 experts from eight different countries with eight different scientific backgrounds, ranging from academics to practicing lawyers to managers of energy communities. The conference will discuss obstacles to the flourishing of Energy Commons along the lines of ‘Legal Forms’ – ‘Community and Participation’ – ‘Scale’. You are cordially invited to participate in the discussions. A livestream will be available (through Webex). We are looking forward to seeing you on Campus Luigi Einaudi in Turin.

For more information on the conference and programme, please [click on this link](#).

To register if you attend physically, [follow this link](#).

NEW MAJOR PUBLICATION: The Exclusionary Effects of the EU Directives

The *Journal of World Energy Law & Business* is publishing the article ‘EU Directives on the Internal Governance of Energy Communities and Their Exclusionary Effects’ by Prof Björn Hoops. It is available open access. You can read the abstract below.

To access the article, follow this link: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jwelb/jwae001>.

A shortened version meant for policymakers and lawmakers is available here: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4679127.

Abstract:

If already existing energy cooperatives and other citizen-led initiatives are to benefit from energy sharing and other privileges under the EU Internal Electricity Market and Renewable Energy Directives, their internal governance will have to adhere to the requirements set by these Directives. This contribution combines legal-doctrinal and empirical research on German energy communities to determine the extent to which different interpretations of the Directives respect established governance structures. It goes on to evaluate which interpretation creates the least disruptive incentives for communities to adapt their internal governance to the Directives. The contribution argues that the Directives should tolerate that energy communities pursue financial goals in addition to economic, environmental, or social benefits. It finds that the exclusion of energy companies, large enterprises, and non-local authorities from membership under the Renewable Energy Directive deters a desirable skill transfer. An exiting member should not be entitled to an immediate reimbursement, to preserve the financial viability of the community. The interpretation of autonomy and effective control should respect the indirect democracy in most communities with few active members leading the way and taking the most important decisions. Finally, the activities and size of the community should inform the interpretation of the proximity requirement.

DATA ON GERMAN ENERGY COMMONS AVAILABLE

This research project has been examining the internal organization and governance of energy cooperatives and other citizen-led initiatives in the energy sector. Some of the data is now freely available and has been used in the publications of the project. 570 statutes of German energy cooperatives have been examined, and 127 citizen-led initiatives have filled in a questionnaire. You can access this data and the analysis freely by clicking on the following links:

- [Analysis of 570 statutes of German energy cooperatives](#);
- [Analysis of 127 responses to the questionnaire](#).

We hope you find the data and publications useful and look forward to collaborating and discussing in the future. Should you have any queries, please do not hesitate to contact us at b.hoops@rug.nl.

Kind regards,

also on behalf of the whole team of 'Private Law and the Energy Commons',

Björn Hoops

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